

The possible pragmatic support of objective humanistic ethics for coaching based training of learning data base systems

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Abstract

The Great Challenges facing us all must necessarily be multidisciplinary, since the complexity we are addressing goes far beyond the mere two-dimensional intelligence linked to the problem solving currently available. Ontological complexity also derives from the intersubjective ambiguity of terms. Suffice it to say that, contrary to what happens in the technical-scientific and semantic environment, the same word and the same value term can have different definitions and standards from person to person. In this, rationality constitutes more of a limit than a potential. Human heuristic thinking provides mental shortcuts that are both rational and emotional, analogical and experiential. Recent studies by AIHC (Italian Health Coaching Association) proved a relevant role of humanistic ethics in all the humanistic transformation processes, according with the Digital Humanism Manifesto of Vienna. If only data base systems can somehow simulate these dynamics, they will be able to act as an even closer complement to an optimal scenario of Human-Tech social development which the NHS Health Education UK has defined as the "Empathy Economy"

Keywords

Digital humanism, Human-tech, health coaching, ethics

Position paper

Following the diffusion and incipient social impact of learning Data Base Systems (DBS - Artificial Intelligence - AI), the European Council found itself repeatedly discussing the ethical principles related to their adoption and their impact [1]. A critical point of this aspect is undoubtedly the first generation computational approach, which essentially involves an intelligence-based approach aimed at statistical analyzes on Big Data which are of an inductive nature and relating to correlations rather than cause-and-effect relationships: in this current generation of cybernetic models we observe that something happens, without being interested in why, in causal terms [2]. Hence the criticisms on ethical stability and reliability, presented in the recent document "Ethical guidelines for reliable AI" issued by the EU [3].

What we are now advocating is the progressive evolution of machine learning towards more complex second generation logical and semantic models that can incorporate a causal model that investigates in the first instance the relationship between phenomena that occur, and therefore their why. At a third, more advanced level, one can imagine that this cause-and-effect relationship could lead to describing and modeling a logic that is representative of the sense of purpose, that is, of Values and Ethics that also take social and environmental well-being into consideration [4].

Considering this situation, is more and more evident today that every ethical interaction follows rational and emotional human relationships dynamics. In this position paper we want to share some reflections on:

- a growing impact of sensitivity to ethical issues and values in society
- the confluence of Humanistic Transformation in Digital Humanism as Human-Tech path
- the correspondent availability of pragmatic ethical models in use in Evolutionary Coaching
- the different complexity of ethical issues (3D) compared to technological models (2D)
- a possible role of Coaching in general and Health Coaching in particular in addressing this complexity.

Coaching in general is dedicated to preserving well-being and personal productive behaviour, Health Coaching in particular works through a pragmatic ethical humanism by applying maieutic in a modern key. Thanks to this, it could play a partnership role in every kind of technical and societal transformation. Indeed, some recent literature evidence points to some inconsistencies between the classic executive coaching techniques and the new needs [5]. These coaching models would not seem suitable for dealing with the ethical switch driven by current social evolution. Values and their meaning are more and more significant for individuals, especially in the last two generations on Millennials and Generation Z [6]. This social inducted trend is confirmed and described in a non-specific way as a phenomenon defined as "Ethical Coaching" [7]. Based on these bibliographical references, it is as if the evolutionary needs of the various generations, in adapting to social change, are concise with an increasingly relevant importance of humanistic ethical principles. Driven by this empirical observation, coaching, due to its pragmatic and non-judgmental characteristics, has equally adapted to the needs of its generational clientele, making available all the useful tools for satisfying their personal and professional growth needs [8]. We may ask ourselves the reason for this concentration of ethical needs. From our point of view, an explanation could be given by the corresponding needs that health coaching found itself having to satisfy, considering that the well-being of the person is its first mandate. The simplest explanation could be that in the social environment these needs were not satisfied, so subsequent generations radicalized this demand for ethicality. All this makes the approach to ethics applied to Data Base Systems even more delicate and critical, given the high sensitivity of the new generations to the moral issue, on which they are not willing to make discounts or compromise. Some examples of this are phenomena such as company turnover and difficulties in talent acquisition.

For this reason, the question relating to the roots of Health Coaching and the profound principles of an applied practical ethics that places the person at the center has recently arisen. Evidences emerging from a recent AIHC (Italian Health Coaching Association) philological study conducted in the field of Ethics and Social Philosophy identified "A Man for Himself" (Erich Fromm) as the main reference for a humanistic coaching on the side of the Man and his well-being: "*To know what is good for man, we need to know his nature. Humanistic ethics is the science applied to the art of living, based on the theoretical science of man...*" [9]. The ethical and practical foundation of Health Coaching is based on these and other concepts of Erich Fromm's thought and today comes as a useful partner in several fields of application of Cultural and Social Transformation. As the Scientific Committee of the Italian Health Coaching Association, our mission coincides exactly with the evolution of the individual's sense of purpose, in its logic related to objective humanistic ethics. In this we noted how the thought of Erich Fromm and other authors of Critical Thinking and Pragmatism specifically analyzed apparently evanescent phenomena such as motivation, moral choice and ethical principles. This fact can constitute the opportunity for a meeting point between science and philosophy in finding the right balance in methodological approaches [10].

In this sense, our commitment to innovation has begun to produce models based on objective humanistic ethics and pragmatic thinking, in fields of application such as the Human-Tech relationship [11], and digital managerial transformation [12]. These congress papers were proposing philological-based models of the integration of the person with the algorithm, in line with the Digital Humanism principles (Vienna Manifesto on Digital Humanism, 2019), which has brought AIHC into contact with a nascent movement of international neo-humanism [13]. As communicated in the Humanistic Transformation conference in Berlin [14], neuroscience explains well what the advantages of a profound attitude of awareness of the operator are, given that the mental state selects external signals based on beliefs and personal experiences. The first to have this intuition was William James, who described how concentrating on one aspect of reality "involves the withdrawal of the mind from some things in order to be able to operate on others with great efficiency" [15].

Today we know that perceptual filters can be self-induced by endogenous cueing, in which the orientation of attention is voluntary, guided by the participant's goals [16]. On the other hand, it is now well known that the social and emotional context has a strong prevalence on the moral behaviour of the individual [17] [18], according with a smithian ethical model [19]. For this reason, it is important to have ethical models that guarantee the integrity of the person. To the vision of ethical

change, our observation added valuable elements not addressed before and a more ontological and humanistic interpretation [20].

In order to give a specific example of what the contribution of Health Coaching could be in a partnership on the ontological modeling of internal ethical thinking behaviors, we refer to a specific explanation of the current problem that learning DBS have encountered. Returning to the previous observation on their current limit related only to the statistical processing of probabilities, related to the computation of possible options, a concept from Erich Fromm's Humanistic Ethics admirably explains the reasons for this limit. It is what distinguishes Intelligence from Rationality and Reason. In these three evolutionary stages of logic, the effective performance of problem solving is two-dimensional and typical of Intelligence, and is independent of the sense of purpose and therefore of the why, while beyond Rationality, which fully describes the cause-and-effect relationships, we find Reason, which investigates motivation, sense of purpose, moral and ethical why in a three-dimensional way [21]. This aspect alone makes us direct witnesses and in some way responsible in being able to provide some contribution to an ethical evolution of the Human-Tech relationship. In reality, the key to understanding Fromm's Sociological and Searle's Social Ontological models [22] [23], also provides precious foundations in considering the dynamics of a prescriptive, performative and moral nature. Much of the Health Coach profession is based on the use of maieutics, on the use of questions and, for example, linguistic and semantic distinctions, typical of the ontological-transformational method [24]. Many of the motivational dynamics of change involve a cultural transformation, which is productive of a variation in linguistic models, which are the anchor and basis of a new social thought and a new reality. These models are often related, in fact, to needs, emotions, desires, suggestions of a desired future. Exploring this type of dynamics through the lens of the direct experience of professional Coaching can be of interest for computational ontology, even more so in the specific case of Health Coaching. Among the various types of Coaching, Health Coaching itself poses a great and specific attention to the ethical aspect, being the protagonist of the recent moral shift in supporting the empowerment of the individual in the sense of their own wellbeing and the natural development of their potential. In this area there are some specific evidence-based reference models on which we can work and co-create an ontological ethical model.

In reporting a final example of the possible practical contribution of Health Coaching, we refer to another field of application linked to ethical aspects and specifically to Value systems. The field of Cultural Transformation is guided by specific models such as those of Dilts [25], Dolan [26] and Barrett [27]. Our practical role is to lead the cognitive-emotional evolution towards the change of one's own moral laws through a dialectic with the client or the groups. As pragmatic operators of the theoretical models proposed by the various authors, we are able to produce a systemic and operational synthesis of the various approaches. From our experience it emerges that each of them has actually defined one of the aspects of the three-dimensional complexity of the "sense of purpose" or the "reason" advocated by Fromm. As an example we can indicate how while Robert Dilts dedicated himself specifically to the cataloging and definition of logical levels, proposing dialogic algorithms, while Barrett was inspired by Maslow's motivational levels [28], to produce a classification of Values that reproduced different levels of self-actualization, with particular attention to the modeling of social groups. Finally, Simon Dolan dedicated himself specifically to the dynamic aspect of internal moral laws, with a triaxial system that allows the person to balance the motivational components according to what is "healthy and right" for him and for the possible organization of belonging.

At this point our curiosity as health coaches makes us ask:

How well known are these evidence-based models?

If they are known, how were they integrated into the system?

How were the assumptions of ethics, non-conflict, morality and respect for minorities respected in considering the foreseeable output?

What could be the possible consequences of ignoring or underestimating these models, widely used in promoting Cultural Transformation and Wellbeing?

In this position paper AIHC propose itself as partner in the co-creation of ethical models inspired by humanistic and human-centric nature, as practical and empirical operators in the direct application of various moral theories in the field. From our point of view, the challenge facing us all must necessarily be multidisciplinary, since the complexity we are facing goes far beyond the mere two-dimensional intelligence linked to the problem solving currently available. Ontological complexity

also derives from the intersubjective ambiguity of terms. Suffice it to say that, contrary to what happens in the technical-scientific and semantic environment, the same word and the same value term can have different definitions and standards from person to person. In this, rationality constitutes more of a limit than a potential. Human heuristic thinking provides mental shortcuts that are both rational and emotional, analogical and experiential and used in problem solving and decision making. “Dual process” theories of cognition (DPT) expounds the theory of “System 1” and “System 2”. In general, System 1 is fast and emotional and “System 2,” is slower, and more governed and controlled. [29]. Learning DBS can try somehow to simulate these dynamics in some more technical application, like interactive systems, due to the bi-dimensional nature of the available engineering models [30]. After that, they have to take up the challenge of the three-dimensional complexity of the moral ethical model, based on the relationship between the individual and the community. A first example, although still two-dimensional, of this complexity is represented by the Meaning Discovery Canvas, which shows all the complexity of the subject-collectivity dynamic, when, for example, related to the academic and research activity of Robert Kegan. A commitment that promoted a constructive-developmental perspective of growth in modeling the human ability to evolve as an individual within the community, based on ethical and moral norms [31]. Someone considers the subjectivity of human beings as deliberately reported as a “limit” rather than a “potential”.

But, in the end, what are learning database systems?

A collection of subjective opinions, which ultimately elaborate a final subjective opinion, relevant only from a probabilistic point of view. Probably identical expression of a unique subject of the observed population. How can we define this output as objective?

What elements define it as real and reliable? Real and reliable for whom?

If from a technological point of view the biases can be sustainable, on ethical and moral issues, what can be the possible consequences on discrimination of diversity?

What seems to loom is the limit of learning DBS as devices created to produce a unique result.

The techno-monistic approach of these applications have been compatible with technological applications so far. What about ethics?

In the new game to be played, how will DBS learning developers be able to accommodate the paradox?

How will they be able to include multiplicity and its incoherence?

Which computational model will be able to correspond to respect for minorities and different ethical and moral sensitivities?

Some false perception think that Pragmatic Ethics in Coaching supports individuals “in *aligning* their internal ethical frameworks with the complex, often externally-driven, moral landscapes we navigate daily”. It's exactly the opposite. In Management Team Coaching, for example, we ask the teammates to co-create a shared natural vision based on true and authentic personal values, protecting the individual and team core from external influences. The flow is reversed, producing, exactly as in mechanical physics, a final resultant of the forces expressed in the field. It is an approach that envisages open innovation open to value dialogue and which promptly eliminates all the toxic values of the system.

Health Coaching, being non-judgmental by its prerogative, knows and welcomes all this aspects, modulating and facilitating it. Today he offers his point of view and his knowledge to open a new scientific debate.

The need to outline the feasibility of a partnership, its potential limitations and any previous experience was rightly mentioned in the discussion with the reviewers. We believe we are on the threshold of a new interdisciplinary evolutionary era, where professionals who have never collaborated before will find themselves in dialogue, as is happening here today. The limit of this is precisely the fact of having no precedent, of not speaking a common language, of having conflicting and perhaps distorted visions of the world. This is the limit and this is the strong point of this evolutionary proposal, for the progress of society. As Coaches, we are used to not having answers, because we have total confidence that our interlocutor already has them within himself. Our role is to guarantee models and processes. In this we think our systemic contribute can be relevant, considering that the third generation team coaching has now become eco-systemic coaching [31].

Trying to make a brief summary of what tangible contribution Health Coaching can provide to Human-Tech progress, we list some possible examples:

- its evolutionary humanistic research
- its daily practical application of Digital Humanism
- evidence based models dedicated to values/ethics
- critical thinking offered in a pragmatic way
- metaphorical and semantic representational models
- empirical experiential link with applied philosophy, psychology, sociology and bioethics
- network of professional operators in direct contact with the end user.

Our definitive maieutic role is to ask uncomfortable questions, because they are the ones that lead to the evolution of the person and the system. We hope this partnership will contribute to facilitate an even closer learning DBS complement to an optimal scenario of Human-Tech social development, which the NHS Health Education UK has defined as the "Empathy Economy" [32].

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